

MENTALITY SYSTEM NETWORKING MODEL APPROACH IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF POLICY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE KRATON IN CIREBON CITY

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Abstract

The focus of the research is the description and analysis of policy implementation in the development of palace tourism in the city of Cirebon. While the sub focus of the research is the analysis of the factors that cause the implementation of the palace tourism development policy in the city of Cirebon has not been effective. The analysis is based on the theory of policy implementation of the Mentality, System and Networking (MSN) Approach. The research method used is a qualitative method. Qualitative methodology is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observed behavior. The research strategy in the qualitative approach used is a case study strategy. Based on the results of the research that the Palace still preserves the values of local cultural wisdom. The design of an effective policy implementation model to develop Keraton tourism in the City of Cirebon based on the Mentality, System, and Networking (MSN) Approach model 2015-2025. RIPPARDA West Java Province 2015-2025 and RIPPARDA Cirebon City 2019-2025 are regulations as the legal basis for developing palace tourism in Cirebon City. In the MSN Approach Model, this System Approach will affect the implementation of the palace tourism development policy in Cirebon City.

Keywords: Mentality System Networking, Tourism Development, Policy

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector in Indonesia is a development sector with great potential to increase state foreign exchange and regional income. According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, tourism is a variety of tourism activities and is supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, businessmen, government and local governments. Visiting a certain place for the purpose of recreation, personal development, or learning the uniqueness of the tourist attraction visited on a temporary basis. Meanwhile, tourism is all activities related to tourism and are multidimensional and multidisciplinary in nature that arise as a manifestation of the needs of each person and country as well as interactions between tourists and local communities, fellow tourists, local governments and entrepreneurs.

Tourism in Indonesia is a very strategic sector because Indonesia has many competitive and comparative advantages in the form of natural conditions, flora, fauna, ancient heritage, historical heritage, art, and culture. The advantages that Indonesia has are resources and capital for tourism development to increase the prosperity and welfare of the people. The tourism sector is very strategic because it has a multiplier effect on other development sectors. Through

tourism development in an area, the welfare of the community will increase, especially those who depend on the tourism sector for their lives.

Tourism development at the national level is carried out based on the National Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPARNAS), while at the regional level it is carried out based on the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPARDA). There are three keys to successful tourism development, namely accessibility, amenities and attractions. Tourism accessibility is all types of transportation facilities and infrastructure that support the movement of tourists from the area of origin of tourists to tourism destinations in relation to the motivation of tourist visits. Tourism amenities are tourism facilities, namely all types of facilities that are specifically intended to support the creation of convenience, comfort, and safety of tourists in visiting tourism destinations. Tourist attractions are tourist attractions, both natural and artificial, that are in an area and have attractions that can bring tourists, for example beaches, lakes, mountains, cultural sites, parks, industries, exhibitions, and others.

West Java Province is one of the provinces in Indonesia that has become a tourist destination because it has diverse and interesting tourism potentials that are spread in every district/city in the form of natural beauty, ancient relics, historical heritage, arts, and culture. This potential is a resource and capital for tourism development in West Java. In the Regional Regulation of West Java Province Number 8 of 2008 concerning the Implementation of Tourism in Article 2 it is stated that the purpose of organizing tourism is in order to mobilize all tourism potential in the region so that it can develop optimally and functionally, in harmony with the religious and cultural values of the community. . Then in Article 4 it is stated that tourism has the function of meeting the physical, spiritual and intellectual needs of every tourist with recreation and travel as well as increasing regional income to realize democracy, equality and unity.

One of the areas in West Java that has been designated as a tourism city pilot is Cirebon City. The development of Cirebon City is very fast compared to other districts and cities in West Java. This is because the location of Cirebon City is geographically very strategic, which is located on the north coast of the island of Java which borders West Java and Central Java. Tourism in the city of Cirebon is also supported by infrastructure facilities, namely the presence of the Cipali toll road, the Trans Java toll road from Cikampek to Cirebon, Semarang, Solo, Surabaya to Pasuruan, the construction of a double track railway that connects the city of Cirebon with other areas. In addition, there is West Java International Airport in Kertajati Majalengka which is the second largest airport after Soekarno-Hatta airport which serves domestic travel.

Cirebon city has great tourism potential that needs to be developed properly, namely as follows:

1. Cultural tourism, namely the Kasepuhan Palace, Kanoman Palace, Kacirebonan Palace, Keprabonan Palace, Sang Cipta Rasa Great Mosque, Kalijaga Site / Monkey Park, Suyaragi Cave Park, and petilasan-petilasan in Cirebon City.
2. Artificial tourism is Taman Ade Irma Suryani/Cirebon Water Park.
3. Coastal tourism, namely Kejawan Beach and Kesenden Beach.

4. Historical tourism, namely the Chinatown area and the Arab Village area.
5. Culinary tourism typical of Cirebon is empal gentong, Jamblang rice, gejrot tofu, lengko rice, koclok noodles, bat satay, and others.
6. Shopping tours in various traditional markets, malls and shopping centers.
7. Creative economy tourism, namely culinary, artistic attractions, souvenirs and others.

This great potential causes Cirebon City to be positioned as the center of the Greater Cirebon Metropolitan (MCR) as a city of culture and history as well as tourism development within the framework of local wisdom. Cirebon city is one of the areas in the archipelago that has a long history of Islamic culture and as an old city full of historical stories with religious and cultural nuances because it became one of the centers for the spread of Islam in West Java by one of the Wali Sanga, namely Sunan Gunung Jati who He is also the Sultan of the Cirebon Sultanate. The city of Cirebon is also known as one of the historic cities that has a unique characteristic because in this city there are three palaces which are fragments of the Cirebon Sultanate which once triumphed in the 15th to 18th centuries. The city of Cirebon as a city of culture and history was then made into the Vision of the City of Cirebon 2018-2023, namely "SEHATI (Healthy, Green, Religious, and Innovative) We Make Cirebon City a Creative City Based on Culture and History".

The development of tourism in the City of Cirebon is to realize the Vision of the City of Cirebon through the Regional Regulation of the City of Cirebon Number 7 of 2019 concerning the Master Plan for Regional Tourism Development (RIPPARDA) of the City of Cirebon for 2019-2025. RIPPARDA is a legal umbrella and guideline in the implementation of planned, integrated and sustainable tourism development in Cirebon City. In the Cirebon City RIPPARDA Article 5, the vision of Cirebon City Regional Tourism Development is set, namely "The realization of Cirebon City as a world-class tourist destination, which is integrated, sustainable and based on regional history and culture".

The palace is one of the leading tourism potentials in the city of Cirebon because in the city of Cirebon there are four palaces, namely the Kasepuhan Palace, Kanoman Palace, Kacirebonan Palace, and the Keprabonan Palace. These four palaces are cultural sites of Cirebon City which are witness to the cultural epicenter which is a local and international attraction. The existence of these four palaces is a comparative advantage of the city of Cirebon because not all regions in Indonesia have palaces. In addition, in contrast to Yogyakarta and Solo, each of which only has one palace, Cirebon City has four palaces. One of the palaces in the city of Cirebon, namely the Kasepuhan Palace, has a historical role as a center for the spread of Islam in West Java by Sunan Gunung Jati who is also the Sultan of the Cirebon Sultanate.

Before the RIPPARDA of Cirebon City was established, palace tourism in Cirebon City had been designated as a leading tourism in the RIPPARDA of West Java Province for 2015-2025. In the RIPPARDA of West Java Province, Cirebon City is designated as the center of the Greater Cirebon Provincial Tourism Destination (DPP). The implication is that Cirebon City is the Center for Historical Tourism Development Strategic Area (KSPP) and the Cirebon

Palace and its surroundings. In more detail, it is stated in Article 22, namely the KSPP Development Plan for the Historical Tourism Area and the Palace in the City of Cirebon and its surroundings, namely:

1. The development theme is historical tourism and the palace.
2. The development target is history-based integrated tourism and the Cirebon palace.
3. Primary tourist attractions include the Kasepuhan Palace, Kacirebonan, Kanoman, Kaprabonan, and Sang Ciptarasa Great Mosque Areas in the Cirebon City Region, as well as the Sunan Gunung Jati Tomb Area in Cirebon Regency.
4. Secondary tourist attractions include the Sunyaragi Cave Water Park, Kesenden Beach, Ade Irma Suryani Park, Kejawan Beach, and Kalijaga Park in the Cirebon City Region, as well as the Talun and Trusmi Batik Areas in the Cirebon Regency area.

The policy for the development of palace tourism in Cirebon City which is stipulated in the RIPPARDA of West Java Province for 2015-2025 and the RIPPARDA of Cirebon City for 2019-2025 must be implemented effectively. According to Kadji (2015: 88), policy implementation departs from the reality that a policy product to be implemented leads directly to three dimensions of policy of stakeholders which include government, private sector, and civil society. A policy implementation will be directed and actual if it pays attention to the mentality, system and networking among the three policy stakeholders. Mentality (mentality) includes attitudes, behavior and responsibilities; the system includes a regulatory system, a cultural value system, an organizational structure and function system, while networking includes a strategic partnership, synergy, and symbiotic mutualism.

METHOD

Method research used is method qualitative. Bogdan and Taylor (1975:5) say that methodology qualitative is procedure research that produces descriptive data in the form of written words or oral of people and observed behavior. Research strategy in approach qualitative that the author Use is a study strategy case according to John W. Creswell (2014:20) In study descriptive this, researcher will describe development tourism in Cirebon City found in the related field with problem research, then analyze it but without count influence from something variable.

Researcher this analyze implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon and the factors that cause implementation not yet effective, will also produce something product in the form of a policy model development tourist effective palace in Cirebon City. Analysis implementation development tourist Keraton in Cirebon City and the factors that cause implementation not yet effective conducted with use method qualitative, while for produce something product in the form of a policy model development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon using Soft System Methodology (SSM) and Research and Development (R & D) methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation Policy Development Tourist The palace in the city of Cirebon.

Palace is one power pull travel and become goals and objectives visit in the city of Cirebon, where have uniqueness, beauty and value in the form of variety variety riches culture and history from the reign of ever successful in Cirebon and still respect tall values culture local Cirebon, as form attention government area for conserve Cirebon city as city culture and history, appropriate The vision of Cirebon City RIPPARDA Number 7 of 2019 is: realization Cirebon city as destination tour world-class, integrated, sustainable, and based on history and culture area.

Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon can see two view that is Palace as Destinations tour that is based on the law Tourism No. 10 of 2009 and Regulations Province West Java Number 8 of 2008 concerning maintenance tourism and RIPPARDA Cirebon City No. 07 of 2019. Keraton as Reserve Culture based on Law no. 11 of 2010. Keraton as destination tour in accordance with Constitution Republic of Indonesia Number; 10 of 2010 concerning maintenance tourism: Destination area next tourism called Destinations tourist is area geographically located in one or more administrative areas in it there is power pull tourism, facilities public, facilities tourism, accessibility, and mutual community related and complementary realization tourism.

According to Provincial Regulations West Java Number: 8 of 2008 concerning maintenance tourism: Destination area next tourism called destination tourist is area or area geographically located in one or more administrative areas in it there is element attractions tourism, facilities public and tourism, accessibility and society, which are mutually related and complementary for realization tourism.

Palace as Reserve Culture based on the law Number 11 of 2010 concerning reserve culture namely: Reserve culture is inheritance culture character material in the form of object Reserve Culture, Building Reserve Culture, heritage site Culture and region reserve culture on land and/or he needs water preserved his existence because have score important for history, science knowledge, education, religion and/ or culture through the determination process.

According to Article 1 Chapter 1 provisions general Law Number: 11 of 2010 concerning reserve culture contain a number of definitions about building reserve culture namely:

- 1) Reserve culture is inheritance culture character material in the form of object reserve culture, building reserve culture, structure reserve culture, Heritage Site Culture and region Reserve Culture on land and/ or in water is necessary preserved his existence because have score important for history, science knowledge, education, religion, and/ or culture through the determination process.
- 2) Reserve objects culture is object nature and or object artificial human, good move nor no moving, in the form of unity or group or its parts, or the remains that have connection close with culture and history development human.

- 3) Building Reserve Culture is arrangement building made from object natural or objects artificial man for Fulfill needs room walled and/ or no walled and roofed.
- 4) Reserve area culture is unit room geography that has two Reserve sites culture or more located close and/ or show distinctive spatial features.

Based on the Mayor's Decree the so the palaces in the city of Cirebon are one of the power pull tour where palace as reserve culture and palace as destination travel. Implementation policy tourist palace as reserve culture based on the law Number 11 of 2010 concerning reserve later culture also strengthened by the Mayor's Decree Number 19 of 2001 concerning Protection and Preservation of Areas and Buildings Reserve Where is the culture in the city of Cirebon? Area The palace in the city of Cirebon is an area reserve necessary culture protected and preserved. Temporary Palace as destination tour based on the law Number 10 of 2009, Provincial Regulation West Java Number 08 of 2008 concerning tourism and RIPPARDA Cirebon City Number 07 of 2019 that palace is an area or area geographically located in the city of Cirebon in it there is element attractions tour culture and history, facilities public and tourism, accessibility and society, which are mutually related and complementary for realization tourism.

2. Policy Development Tour Keraton in Cirebon City Based on Plan Master of Tourism Development Province West Java

Based on Constitution Number 10 of 2009 concerning maintenance tourism in article 8 (1) that in develop tourism in the area so The Provincial Government and Cirebon City Government have Plan Tourism Development Master as guide and umbrella law in maintenance tourism in the region. Development tourism in the palaces in the city of Cirebon as a destination tourist still respect tall score culture in accordance with vision on Provincial Regulations Java Number 15 of 2015 concerning Provincial RIPPARDA West Java in 2015-2025 in article 9 paragraph 1 that: Vision development provincial tourism is make West Java as destination tourist integrated, sustainable and world-class high cultural value.

RIPPAR is a guideline main for planning, management and control development tourism the area that contains the necessary vision, mission, goals, policies, strategies, plans and programs carried out by the holder interest in development tourism. Tourism development conducted based on Plan Regional Tourism Development Master with notice Regulation Government Number 50 of 2011 concerning Plan National Tourism Development Master (RIPPARNAS) and Plans Master of Tourism Development province West Java.

Based on Provincial RIPPARDA West Java then Cirebon Palace became target development tourist based on history and culture because Palace still conserve values wisdom local culture. As form attention in development tourist Keraton in Cirebon Central Government, Government Province West Java and Cirebon City Government every year give budget grant to 4 palaces in the city of Cirebon, namely: Palace Kasepuhan, Keraton Kanoman, Keraton Kacirebonan and the Palace Cirebon City Palace. As stated by Mr. Mostofa as Field tourism at DKOP Cirebon City: Keraton as one destination main industry tourist so that palace Becomes priority and was

given a grant of 4 palaces in the city of Cirebon for maintenance buildings, promotions and attractions culture accepted palace every year. (Interview results January 6, 2020)

Statement This is also supported by palace namely Mr. Andi as Staff manager Palace comfortable that: Central Government, Government the Province and the City Government of Cirebon provide grant for maintenance Palace, budget grant no enough for maintenance palace, grants obtained _ only enough for Fulfill shopping house ladder palace course. Government center through Ministry tourist give grant for whole the palaces in the city of Cirebon in 2014 the master plan conducted that is To do revitalization but new physique only and that only issued only 30% for HR revitalization yet accomplished . (Interview results January 4, 2020)

Temporary based on Interview with The Mayor of Cirebon stated that: Government center, government Province and Government Cirebon city provides grant to palaces in the city of Cirebon for maintenance building Keraton, once in 2012 the government center give grant for revitalization on every palace Cirebon. (Interview results 21 July 2020)

Based on results interview above so could concluded that Based on Provincial Regulations West Java Number 15 of 2015 concerning Provincial RIPPARDA West Java Year 2015-2025 then Cirebon Palace became target development tourist based on history and culture because Palace still conserve values wisdom local culture. Palace is building worth necessary history and culture preserved so as not extinct with development of the times. As form support and care so Central Government, Provincial Government and Regional Government of Cirebon City in maintain preservation valuable building culture and history so prioritize development Keraton in Cirebon City as destination tour based on history and culture with routine budget every grant year development palace in the APBD for maintenance fourth the palace in the city of Cirebon, namely: Palace Kasepuhan, Keraton Kanoman, Keraton Kacirebonan and the Palace Kaprabonan.

3. Policy Development Tour Keraton in Cirebon City Based on RIPPARDA Cirebon City

Vision of RIPPARDA Provincial Regulation West Java Number 15 of 2015 which makes Make West Java as Destinations Tourist World Class Integrate, Sustainable and Upholding Cultural Values. As listed in Article 22 that Strategic Area Development Plan Tourist Province (KSPP) for historical and cultural area is Palace Kasepuhan, Kacirebonan, Kanoman, Kaprabonan who own power pull primary tourism that is still respect high and preserve score culture in West Java.

Development tourist Cirebon city is guided by the policies contained in the in RIPPARDA. Cirebon City Regional Regulation Number 7 of 2019 concerning Plan the Master of Cirebon City Regional Tourism Development 2019-2025 was created as guidelines in maintenance development tourism areas that are planned, integrated and sustainable, as well as aim as guidelines in planning development tourism and maintenance development tourism area.

Vision Cirebon City Regional Tourism based on RIPPARDA Cirebon City is "The realization of Cirebon City as a destination tour world-class, integrated, sustainable, and based on history and culture area." Also, in line with Cirebon City's vision is "Healthy" our make Cirebon City

as city creative based on culture and history? Cirebon city is famous with the city that has a very complete history and culture that has power pull alone for traveler for visit in the city of Cirebon. Form buildings that have history and culture is the palaces in the city of Cirebon which are the proof spread of Islam in West Java.

See the potentials Cirebon city then become very important for set policy by comprehensive for development tourism in the city of Cirebon as stated in Cirebon City Regional Regulation Number 7 of 2019 concerning Plan The new 2019-2025 Cirebon City Regional Tourism Development Master approved by the mayor Cirebon on August 6, 2019.

Vision development tourism Cirebon city, namely: "The realization of Cirebon City as a destination tour world class, integrated, sustainable as well as based on history and culture area." worth it with the Provincial RIPPARDA Where is West Java? Cirebon Palace became priority in development tourism in the city of Cirebon, especially in destinations tourism and culture, according to with destination development tourist the city of Cirebon, namely realize tourist Cirebon city as destination tourist world class based on history and culture as well as values wisdom local.

Cirebon Palace which consists of from palace Kasepuhan, Keraton Kanoman, Keraton Keciirebonan, Keraton Keprabonan is destination travel still hold firm tradition Cirebon culture from grandmother moyan Besides have power pull tour relic past history, tradition Palace this is power pull tours that can enjoyed until cause power pull for people to see and enjoy it. Tradition the still preserved until moment this is in the Cirebon palace. Palaces the is palace Kasepuhan, Keraton Kanoman, Keraton Keciirebonan and the Palace Keprabonan.

4. Implementation Policy Development Tourist Keraton in Cirebon City

Implementation policy is crucial stage in the policy process public, personally simple that implementation policy is Step implementation policy that alone. Implementation policy public is aspect important regarding with Step implementation from something policies that have been taken or decided by actor administration in a process involving amount sources including people, funds, and abilities organizational for reach goals that have been set previously in Thing complete problems public.

Tourism is integral part of development nationally done by systematic, planned and integrated, sustainable and responsible answer with give protection to religious values, lively culture in community, sustainability and quality environment life as well as interest national. Tourist is various type activities travels and supported various facility as well as services provided by the community, entrepreneurs, government, and government area.

Implementation policy used as policy in development tourist The palace in the city of Cirebon is use policy maintenance tourism Constitution Number 10 of 2009 where Palace as destination travel, then Constitution Number 11 of 2010 where palace as object reserve culture in form building and Mayor's Decree Number 19 of 2001 Keraton as need area protected and preserved because palace is area and building reserve culture in the city of Cirebon.

Condition now The Cirebon City Government has implemented policy development Cirebon Palace with to do communication and resources existing power. Implementation communication carried out by the Cirebon City Government through DKOKP as a leading tourism sector in develop tourism Cirebon City Palace, namely with method stage meeting or meeting discussing about problem tourism in the city of Cirebon.

Local government always to do communication with party palace and related parties for discuss the agenda of tourism events that will there right by the palace as well as a collaboration event agenda Among Local Government with party Palace and communication regarding grant funds given tourism Local Government to Palace and training agenda.

Budgeted funds from Cirebon City Regional Government which is sourced from the APBD is used for activity performing arts and traditional rituals traditional in accordance with the proposed agenda to DKOKP Cirebon City is not under maintenance yet palace buildings and human resources that alone, so for maintenance The palace and the salaries of HR who manage Palace obtained from sale ticket end of the palace.

5. Factors that cause Implementation Policy Development tourist The palace in Cirebon yet effective

Implementation policy according to Kadji (2015:86) that a policy whatever is ready implemented, ensured empties and intersects directly with three dimensions of policy of stakeholders or interested parties with policy namely government, private and civil society. Implementation policy development the palace in the city of Cirebon was strongly influenced by several factors, and in study this writer uses MSN-Approach implementation model study policy from Kadji (2015: 87) namely: Mentality-Approach, System-Approach and Networking-Approach.

Implementation model design policy development tourist palaces in the city of Cirebon based on the MSN Approach and Penta Helix models can depict as following:

- 1) Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon is based on the policy in the form of Plan Parent Development Regional Tourism (RIPPARDA) Province West Java 2015-2025. Inside Article 22 affirmed that one of the Strategic Area Center Developments Development Tourism (KSPP) is a historical tourism area and palace in the city of Cirebon and its surroundings.
- 2) Based on Provincial RIPPARDA West Java 2015-2025 is then prepared RIPPARDA Cirebon City 2019-2025. Inside Article 11 affirmed that palace is one plan structure zoning tourism in Cirebon City. The 2019-2025 Cirebon City RIPPARDA alone arranged based on Cirebon City's vision 2018-2023 is "HEALTHY (Healthy, Green, Religious, Innovative) We Make Cirebon City a Creative City based on Culture and History".
- 3) Provincial RIPPARDA West Java 2015-2025 and the 2019-2025 Cirebon City RIPPARDA is regulation as base law development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon. In the MSN Approach Model, regulation this is part of the complete System Approach

consist from regulation, value culture, as well structure and function organization. In the MSN Approach Model, this System Approach will influence implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon.

- 4) Policy in the form of Provincial RIPPARDA West Java 2015-2025 and the 2019-2025 Cirebon City RIPPARDA then implemented in development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon.
- 5) Stakeholders or the actors involved in implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon, namely: palace, Cirebon City Government, sector private sector, and community. Besides it is necessary involvement from academics and the press/media.
- 6) Stakeholders or the actors involved in implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon in Networking Approach perspective is necessary build partnership strategic, synergy, and symbiosis mutualism. This Networking Approach will influence implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon.
- 7) Stakeholders or the actors involved in implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon in Mentality Approach perspective is necessary realized attitude, behavior, and responsibility effective answer. This Mentality Approach will also influence implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon.
- 8) Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon also needs implement other factors that become novelty (novelty) of study writer namely the political will of the head area, leadership head area, culture organization, and motivation. Factors as a novelty it will also influence implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon.
- 9) Implementation policy development tourist palace in Cirebon City which applies the Mentality Approach, System Approach, and Networking Approach, as well as research novelty writer, then will come true implementation policy development tourist effective palace in Cirebon City.
- 10) Implementation policy development tourist effective palace in Cirebon City will cause palace Becomes destination tour superior in the city of Cirebon.
- 11) If the palace capable Becomes destination tour superior in the city of Cirebon, then will support achievement Cirebon City's vision 2018-2023 is "HEALTHY (Healthy, Green, Religious, Innovative) We Make Cirebon City a Creative City based on Culture and History".

CONCLUSION

Policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon can seen from two view that is Palace as Destinations tour that is based on the law Tourism No. 10 of 2009 and Regulations Province West Java Number 8 of 2008 concerning maintenance tourism and RIPPARDA Cirebon City No. 07 of 2019 and the Palace as Reserve Culture guided by Law no. 11 of 2010.

The Cirebon Palace became target development tourist based on history and culture because Palace still conserves values wisdom local culture. Palace is building worth necessary history and culture preserved so as not extinct with development of the times. As form support and care so Central Government, Provincial Government and Regional Government of Cirebon City in maintain preservation valuable building culture and history so prioritize development Keraton in Cirebon City as destination tour based on history and culture with routine budget every grant year development palace in the APBD for maintenance fourth the palace in the city of Cirebon, namely: Palace Kasepuhan, Keraton Kanoman, Keraton Kecirebonan and the Palace Keprabonan.

Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon in Dimensions of Mentality-Approach (Approach mentality) which consists of from attitude, behavior and responsibility answer Government Cirebon city against development tourist Palace not yet walk optimally like still existence limitations Support budget for development tourist The palaces in the city of Cirebon. Mentality-Approach consisting of from attitude, behavior and responsibility answer researcher conclude still half heart for development palace them because party palace still limit self with the authority it has so that government Cirebon city is not could totality or follow mix in setting development Palace that alone. Given budget Government the city of Cirebon in the Cirebon City Budget only could sufficient for part small activity palace not yet for maintenance palace, so that Palace in to do maintenance and traditional events that have not been covered by APBD using income originating from ticket enter visitors. Ticket entrance earned by the Palace no deposited to Local Government as Cirebon City Original Revenue (PAD) enters to income palace. Authority this is what makes implementation policy development tourist Cirebon city yet running optimally.

Dimensions System–Approach consisting of: System Regulation, System Culture and System Structure and Function Organization already implemented only not optimal. On system regulation, Form Support to development tourism in the city of Cirebon, where the palace in the city of Cirebon has potency history and culture area in accordance with vision development Cirebon City Regional tourism, namely: The realization of Cirebon City as a destination tour world-class, integrated, sustainable, and based on history and culture area. On implementation still not yet running optimally because Palace have authority in management The palace, the local government doesn't could intervene and join mix in the palace's internal affairs, different with in Yogyakarta the Regional Government is led by the Sultan of the Keratonyogyakarta so that totality in develop the palace. There is still sectoral ego in development Keraton in Cirebon City, Mayor as leader Regional Government of Cirebon City and Sultan as Leader Stakeholder custom that has authority in management the palace so that running respectively and compartmentalized.

Dimensions of Networking-Approach (approach network) consisting of from partnership Strategic, Synergy, Symbiosis Mutualism not yet implemented optimally viewed from role between departments in regional government, private sector which has not been optimal in terms of support through its CSR , the role of Schools and Colleges in promote and include payload local in curriculum learning, role society too not optimal in participate and be aware

tour in develop tourist Keraton in Cirebon City, Novelty or update in study about implementation policy from The theory put forward by Kadji (2015) is: theory three approach in implement something policy namely : 1). Mentality-Approach (Approach Mentality), 2) System-Approach (Approach System), 3) Networking-Approach (approach Network cooperation). Researcher find field updates there is other factors that have not stated by Kadji (2015). Factors not yet is in theory Kadji (2015) is a novelty (novelty theory obtained from results research) namely as the following: 1) Political Will of the Regional Head; 2) Leadership Regional Head; 3) Culture Organization; 4) Motivation.

Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon is based on the policy in the form of Plan Parent Development Regional Tourism (RIPPARDA) Province West Java 2015-2025. Inside Article 22 affirmed that one of the Strategic Area Center Developments Development Tourism (KSPP) is a historical tourism area and palace in the city of Cirebon and its surroundings.

Implementation policy development tourist the palace in the city of Cirebon also needs implement other factors that become novelty (novelty) of study writer namely the political will of the head area, leadership head area, culture organization, and motivation. Factors as a novelty it will also influence implementation policy development tourist palace in the city of Cirebon. Implementation policy development tourist the palace in Cirebon City which applies the Mentality Approach, System Approach, and Networking Approach, as well as research novelty writer, then will come true implementation policy development tourist effective palace in Cirebon City.

Implementation policy development tourist effective palace in Cirebon City will cause palace Becomes destination tour superior in the city of Cirebon. If the palace capable Becomes destination tour superior in the city of Cirebon, then will support achievement Cirebon City's vision 2018-2023 is "HEALTHY (Healthy, Green, Religious, Innovative) We Make Cirebon City a Creative City based on Culture and History". If the vision of Cirebon City 2018-2023 is achieved, then will increase development region, Regional Original Income (PAD), and welfare people in Cirebon City.

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